

FELLOWSHIP

April 2025

Uttarpara Kotrung City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

Nāgrika does not independently verify all the facts or statements in this document and does not assume responsibility for any errors, inaccuracies, or inconsistencies. The use of Nāgrika’s branding denotes the document’s origin within a guided fellowship process, not an endorsement of specific content. The document has been formatted by Nāgrika for presentation consistency; no edits have been made to the fellow’s original content.

All images used in this document are sourced from the author themselves, in case otherwise credited.

© 2025 Nagrika Policy Research Foundation.

This work was created as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship, partly supported by Rohini Nilekani Philanthropies, and is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)

Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

Contents

05	Introduction
06	History of Uttara para
10	Everyday Life
14	Voices of Concern
17	Dreams for Tomorrow
19	Conclusion
20	References
22	Message from the Founders

Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Uttarpara

উত্তরপাড়া খুব পুরোনো একটি শহর। পুরোনো উত্তরপাড়ার সাথে বর্তর্তমান এই শহরটার আকাশ পাতাল তফাৎ। পুরোনো উত্তরপাড়ার মানুষজন একে অপরকে চিনতো, জানতো, নিয়মিত কথাবার্ত্তা হতো। কিন্তু বর্তর্তমান সময় বদলেছে, মানুষের জীবনও অনেক বদলে গেছে। সকলেই সময়ে র সাথে দৌড়োতে বাধ্য হচ্ছে। এখন নতুন প্রজন্মের মানুষেরা একে ওপর কে প্রায় চেনে না বললেই চলে, আর চিনলেও কথা বলার সময়টুকু নেই। হয়তো, একেই শহরকরণ বলে।

Uttarpara is a very old city. The present city is in stark contrast to the old Uttarpara. In the past, the people of Uttarpara knew each other well and interacted regularly. However, life has changed significantly over the years. Today, life feels like a race against time. The new generation often hardly knows their neighbours, and even if they do, they rarely have time to engage in conversation. But isn't this what urbanization looks like? - Mani Roy

History of Uttarpara

I can't think of starting to talk about Uttarpara without some historical context to situate the origins of my city.

It was the year 1704 when zamindar Ratneswar Roychowdhury left his ancestor's house and created a new residence called “*Ootarpara*” (in Bengali, Ootarpara literally means northern part, in this case, north of Bally town). Back then, it was mostly marshland.

The primary occupation of Uttarpara at that time was fishing, while some areas were known for dacoits. Over time, between 1800 and 1900, the village started developing into a proper town with palatial buildings, schools, hospitals, a public library, a police station, a post office, and other essential services.

Figure 1: Uttarpara Public Library
Source: Google

History of Uttarpara

In 1795, Hooghly District was formed from Burdwan District, and by 1814, Baidyhati Police Station became part of Hooghly, bringing Uttarpara under its administration. Until 1843, Uttarpara was part of the 24-Parganas District. In 1916, a separate Uttarpara Police Station was set up to cater to the town's growing needs. (Municipality, 2024)

To look at it from a governance lens, Uttarpara is governed by the Uttarpara Kotrung Municipality, one of the oldest civic bodies in West Bengal, established in 1853. This municipality is responsible for the administration and development of the region, providing essential civic services such as water supply, sanitation, solid waste management, street lighting, and upkeep of public infrastructure.

The municipality is divided into 24 wards. For law and order, the area falls under the jurisdiction of the Uttarpara Police Station, which is part of the Chandannagar Police Commissionerate.

INTRODUCTION

Although Uttarpara did not become an industrial hub, it emerged as a center of intellect and education. "We have always been known for our learning." Ours was the first town in the Hooghly district to establish an English-medium school—not just funded by the British and the zamindar but by the community itself. That shows how much we value education." - Mani Roy

In 1846, the Uttarpara Government High School was opened, and in 1859, the town established the Uttarpara Jaykrishna Library, which was also India's first free public library.

"This library isn't just a building; it holds a special place in the hearts of everyone in Uttarpara. It carries great historical significance. It has been frequently visited by prominent figures like Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo, and even Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose. A particularly noteworthy story is how poet Michael Madhusudan Dutta spent the last few months of his life here, on the first floor of the old building."
- Manis Dey

Figure 3: Uttarpara Government High School
Source: Google

INTRODUCTION

At this very place, Sri Aurobindo delivered his famous Uttarpara Speech in May 1909, unveiling "the realization of the ultimate" to the public. The Uttarpara Speech holds immense significance as it marked Sri Aurobindo's transformation from a revolutionary to a sage. The library's historical importance was emphasized by Rathindra Chattopadhyay in Desh Patrika on 18th May 1960, referring to it as "an endangered historical monument." (Jha, 2024).

Finally, in 1853, the Uttarpara Municipality was formed, making it the oldest municipality in West Bengal. This short historical backdrop would give some idea of what the city looked like back in those days. Uttarpara has undergone significant transformation in recent years and is catching up to other cities in terms of urbanization. This city used to have ponds and wide fields, but now it is filled with apartments. Stories of longing, change, and an unwavering hope for a better future are carried by the people of Uttarpara across generations. Their voices create a vision of a city at the crossroads of nostalgia and modernity.

Figure 4: Map of ward-wise city division
Source: Google

Everyday Life

পুরানো সে ই দি নে র কথা Stories of the Past

I chose to initiate the thematic discussions with a beautiful Rabindra Sangeet because there is a stereotype that people from Bengal are obsessed with nostalgia. Who could articulate the feeling of nostalgia better than Rabindranath Thakur? For those who have seen Uttarpara through the decades, the shift has been drastic.

P. Roy, an 83-year-old senior citizen, sighs heavily as he recalls the green fields where he once played. “There is nothing in this city that I am still proud of,” he admits, his words carrying the weight of loss. The city he knew has vanished, replaced by concrete structures.

Mani Roy, a 53-year-old teacher, shares a similar sentiment. “Previously, there were many trees, and the area looked beautiful, especially in February and March.” She describes a childhood filled with simple pleasures—sitting by the pond, chatting with friends, and cherishing an occasional ice cream. Today, those pockets of joy have been replaced by hurried lives and endless traffic.

Figure 5: Bird's eye view of Uttarpara
Source: Google

Everyday life in a fast-urbanising Suburb

The fields where people played are now apartments. The roads are wider, but they are busier, filled with hurried commuters rather than the slow, familiar faces. My city seems to have changed a lot, but the people still hold onto their past, whether through the way they narrate their stories, the ghats (mainly Doltola Ghat) they visit, or the Jaykrishna Library that they are proud of. The city may have lost its open spaces and close community feeling, but its people still remember its essence.

That summed up his weekend. Although he still visits there, he likes to spend his time outside the city more often. This highlights his growing need to find a balance between growing speed, city life, and quieter village environments.

For college students, this case is very different. When I asked Haripriya about her daily routine when she lived in Hubli. She narrates her college days. Very plain and simple, she says her college time revolved around “going to college, coming back home, going to the gym with Aishwarya, and then hanging out with her friends at the Chai Shai, which was right below the gym.” She narrates on her monotonous schedule revolving around bunking college, going to the gym, and hanging out in the cafe.

Figure 6 : A small shop by the road selling variety of stuff
Source: Author

The city's transformation

The city has grown undeniably. Roads are wider, well-lit, and mostly clean; now we have more hospitals and even a few shopping malls. Yet, growth has not been uniform, nor has it been inclusive. The narratives portray an interesting insight where some citizens think that everyday life has improved for the people of Uttarpara; for instance, a councillor highlights how the city has nearly everything—hospitals, schools, and libraries. Basically, everything people need to live.

However, upon asking if there were any shortcomings, she mentioned that “there’s a lack of sufficient washrooms and employment opportunities.” She adds that previously, if someone had to use the washroom or ask for water, they could have easily asked, but now things have changed. People don’t like getting bothered by others. “*Sohor hoye jaache*”(Getting urbanized now).

Another active citizen mentioned how things have changed for the better in Uttarpara, and by better she meant more urbanized. She mentioned how there’s religious tolerance here, and that makes her quite comfortable living here. Another citizen pointed out how “*our municipality even won the prize for being the cleanest in the Hooghly district. And despite all the change, people still have a strong sense of community here.*”

Figure 7: Still of wide roads with footpaths
Source: Author

Figure 8: Still of a neighbourhood
Source: Author

Voices of Concern

Is the development accessible, affordable, and meaningful to all?

Not everyone sees this progress the same way. Sabita Murmu, a 38-year-old house help, speaks with grief and frustration. “My son died because of the carelessness of a hospital worker. I don’t have enough money to go to private hospitals.” Her statement highlights the systemic inequalities. The city’s so-called development means little when basic facilities—like safe drinking water and accessible healthcare—remain out of reach. Her voice shakes with anger and longing for a place that truly cares for its people.

Almost all respondents highlighted that there is an urgent need for economic opportunities, more public facilities like washrooms, reliable drinking water, benches, open spaces, more trees, accessible spaces of leisure, and, most importantly, a sense of community. Even though people agree that healthcare facilities have improved a lot, there is a lot of scope for improvement.

Here is one picture of the few drinking water facilities in Uttarpara. Clearly, it lacks maintenance, and the quality of water is quite questionable since people prefer to buy water than to drink from it. Also, another picture shows a seating space created by the citizens because there are hardly any public seating arrangements.

These pictures are from the main road of Uttarpara. The first one is a bus stand, and the second one is a public gym.

All body types should be able to use public facilities; however, in this case, it appears that the footpaths are not very accessible to those with disabilities.

Figure 9: defunct public tap for drinking water
Source: Author

Figure 10: A stone used as public seating space
Source: Author

Gender and right to the city: Who gets to belong?

Using a gender lens is always more effective when discussing accessibility and inclusivity. When viewed through this lens, it is clear that a patriarchal mindset still exists, striving to limit the freedom and accessibility of non-male people. I asked an active citizen about safety in public spaces in Uttarpara, and their response was, “It is relatively safe for women here, but why do 'good women' need to be outside after 10:30 or 11:00 pm?”

When I inquired about the living conditions of transgender people, many seemed perplexed and discomforted. When I pressed further about instances of violence against them, one respondent commented, “Yeh toh hota hi rehta hai, normal hai” (It happens, and it's normal). These statements highlight the urgent need to analyze the city through a gender lens if we genuinely want to create an inclusive and livable environment for everyone.

Raj, an 18-year-old transgender youth, expressed a lifelong feeling of not belonging: “We need a place we can turn to for support, a queer-friendly organization, something that makes this city feel like home.” Soumya, a 21-year-old queer individual, emphasized the necessity for better facilities, opportunities, and, most importantly, a more tolerant neighborhood where their existence doesn't feel wrong. They added, “I want to live somewhere like Salt Lake, where people don't stare at me.”

The longing for anonymity and acceptance is evident in their words. In its current state, Uttarpara fails to provide either, at least according to the narratives shared. Many individuals feel pushed to the margins, with their needs overlooked in the push toward modernization. As Uttarpara moves towards more development, it must ask: Is it growth for all, or only for some?

Dreams for Tomorrow

People's Visions for the Future

Despite its challenges, the people of Uttarpara have not lost hope. There is a longing, almost universal, for a city that finds a balance—between the duality of tradition and modernity. Manis Dey, a 54-year-old active citizen, sees potential. “Our municipality even won the prize for being the cleanest in the Hooghly district.” Cleanest in Hooghly? I'm somewhat concerned about other places if this appears to be the cleanest. The pictures above show that waste management still needs to improve.

Further, he envisions a city with more greenery, beautiful leisure spaces, and a continued sense of community feeling among its people. Ruhi, a 16-year-old student, dreams of opportunities that extend beyond what the city currently offers. “It would be great to have student community clubs where we could exchange ideas, discuss topics, and develop new skills.” The lack of safe spaces for the youth is evident, but so is the desire to create them.

For political leaders, the vision of the city is tied to policy and infrastructure. “We need more developmental projects—flyovers, specialized hospitals—but for that, we need funding.” - A councillor. His perspective, though pragmatic, still holds a note of nostalgia. He acknowledges the cultural richness of Uttarpara's past but insists that moving forward requires investment and political will. His words reflect a classic urban dilemma—how to modernize without erasing history? However, this dilemma could be resolved to some extent through community engagement.

Figure 11: The traffic congestion of this place, especially in the office hours
Source: Author

“It would be great to have student community clubs where we could exchange ideas, discuss topics, and develop new skills.”

Ruhi, 16

Figure 12: The traffic congestion of this place, especially in the office hours
Source: Author

Conclusion

It would be incorrect for me to depict my city as being entirely negative. Uttarpara is not just a physical space but a living memory of the struggles and aspirations of its people. For some, it is a city lost to time. For others, it is a city of unexplored potential. What remains constant is the desire for a home that does not just grow in size but in inclusivity, opportunity, and belonging.

These pictures reflect the busy yet interconnected daily lives of these people. The ability of Uttarpara to listen—to the voices that demand and to the voices that dream—may hold the key to its future.

The lack of safe spaces for the youth is evident, but so is the desire to create them.

Only then will it be able to progress, not as a collection of infrastructures but as a home where all of its citizens can feel at ease and have a sense of belonging. Several immediate changes can be made to improve infrastructural development in Uttarpara. These include adding more washrooms and water facilities, making footpaths accessible, planting and maintaining trees, and enhancing waste management.

Moreover, establishing direct public transport connections to the Dakhineswar metro would be hugely beneficial. For medium to long-term goals, it is essential to provide more employment opportunities and training programs, particularly for small-scale industries. Increased police vigilance is also necessary for safety. Most importantly, fostering a sense of community among citizens through various inclusive public events and activities. These can significantly enhance the livability of Uttarpara.

REFERENCES

Bhattacharya, Akash (2021). Urbanizing Uttarpara: Philanthropy, Improvement, Education, c.1846 to c.1865. doi:10.25360/01-2021-00002.

Jha (2024). Jayakrishna Public Library. Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav, Ministry of Culture, Government of India. <https://cmsadmin.amritmahotsav.nic.in/district-reopsitory-detail.htm?23245>

Municipality, Uttarpara. (n.d.). Uttarpara-Kotrung Municipality. Retrieved February 12, 2025, from <https://www.uttarparamunicipality.in/history-of-uttarpara.html>

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Induja Aich Roy

Induja is a queer feminist and independent scholar from Uttarpara, West Bengal, holding a master's degree in sociology. Her research interests include gender and sexuality-based exclusion, urban spaces, and the sense of belonging. Driven by a passion for social justice, she volunteers with various organisations to advocate for gender equity and inclusivity. In the future, she aspires to pursue a doctoral degree.

Nāgrika Team:

Tarun Sharma | Co-founder

Yutika Vora | Co-founder

Ravjyot Kaur | Research Associate

Praisyy David | Research Associate

Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International

www.nagrika.org

Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International

www.nagrika.org